

Anatomical Variations of the Circle of Willis - A Systematic Review**Krishna Gopal Tailor¹, Prisha Rishi², Satish Kumar Hariouhdh³, Bandita Medhi⁴,
Manjunath V. Motagi⁵**¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore.²Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore.³Postgraduate Resident, Department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore.⁴Professor, Department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore.⁵Professor & HOD, Department of Anatomy, Sri Aurobindo Medical College & PG Institute, Sri Aurobindo University, Indore

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Manjunath V. Motagi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The Circle of Willis (CoW) is a vital anastomotic arterial network at the base of the brain that serves as a collateral circulation system, ensuring adequate blood flow to the brain in case of occlusion. However, it exhibits significant anatomical variations across individuals, impacting cerebral blood flow and susceptibility to neurological disorders. This systematic review aims to comprehensively evaluate the prevalence, types, and clinical implications of anatomical variations in the Circle of Willis.**Methods:** A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane databases. Studies published from 2014 to 2024 that focused on anatomical variations of the CoW were included. A total of 14 studies met the inclusion criteria after a rigorous screening process. Data extraction involved identifying variations, their prevalence, and potential associations with clinical outcomes such as ischemic stroke and aneurysm formation.**Results:** Sample sizes in the selected studies ranged from 73 to 1,864 participants. The average age of participants in different studies ranges from approximately 36 to 72 years, indicating varying demographics across studies. The prevalence of a complete Circle of Willis ranges broadly, with values from as low as 12% in Norway to as high as 74.23% in South Africa.**Conclusion:** This systematic review indicates a complex landscape of anatomical variations in the Circle of Willis, with significant differences in the prevalence of complete and incomplete configurations across various populations.**Keywords:** Circle of Willis, anatomical variations.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The Circle of Willis (CoW) is a vital anastomotic arterial network located at the base of the brain, playing a crucial role in maintaining cerebral perfusion and providing collateral circulation. This structure, named after the 17th-century physician Thomas Willis, is designed to ensure a continuous blood supply to the brain, particularly in cases of arterial occlusion or stenosis.

However, extensive research has demonstrated that the CoW exhibits significant anatomical variations that deviate from the classical description. These variations can include hypoplasia or aplasia of key arteries, such as the anterior communicating artery (AComA) and posterior communicating arteries

(PCoA), as well as the presence of accessory vessels and other anomalies. Recent studies have highlighted the prevalence of these anatomical variations, indicating that over half of the population exhibits some form of deviation from the typical configuration of the CoW.

For instance, a meta-analysis estimated that the overall prevalence of variations is approximately 68.22%, with specific rates of unilateral and bilateral PCoA hypoplasia or aplasia reported at 19.45% and 22.83%, respectively [1]. Such variations are not merely anatomical curiosities; they have profound clinical implications. They can influence the risk of cerebrovascular diseases,

including ischemic strokes and aneurysms, and can complicate surgical interventions. For example, hypoplasia of the PCoA has been associated with an increased incidence of thalamic infarcts, underscoring the importance of understanding these variations in the context of cerebrovascular health [2,3].

Furthermore, the establishment of a universal classification system for these variations is essential for enhancing communication among healthcare professionals and improving patient care outcomes. By systematically cataloging the diverse anatomical configurations of the CoW, clinicians can better anticipate potential complications during neurosurgical procedures and tailor interventions to individual patient anatomy. This systematic review aims to comprehensively evaluate the prevalence, types, and clinical implications of anatomical variations within the Circle of Willis.

The Circle of Willis (CoW) exhibits several common anatomical variations, which can significantly impact cerebral blood flow and clinical outcomes. Hypoplasia or aplasia of the posterior communicating artery (PCoA) is one of the most prevalent variations, with unilateral PCoA hypoplasia found in approximately 19.45% of cases and bilateral aplasia in about 22.83% [1]. Hypoplasia of the anterior communicating artery (ACoMA) is also common, with studies reporting its occurrence in around 8.6% of individuals [4].

The Fetal-type posterior cerebral artery (fPCA), where the PCA retains a fetal origin from the internal carotid artery, is noted in 21.1% of patients. This variant can affect hemodynamics and is associated with an increased risk of ischemic strokes [3, 2].

The presence of additional vessels, such as duplications or triplications of the ACoMA, is observed in about 12% of cases [2, 5]. Incomplete Circle of Willis, characterized by the absence of one or more arteries, occurs in about 6% of specimens studied [2]. Variations in the configuration of the anterior and posterior cerebral arteries, including hypoplastic segments, are also noted, with significant implications for vascular health [1,6].

Method

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guideline [7]. A systematic search was conducted using electronic databases like PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane Library.

The search terms included "circle of Willis" and "anatomical variations" published from 2014 to

2024. We included cross-sectional studies, prospective studies, retrospective studies, descriptive studies, and cohort studies anatomical variations in the Circle of Willis and published in English language. Studies having only abstract and non-access of full text were excluded.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies that provide quantitative data on the prevalence of Circle of Willis variations.
- Studies that investigate the association between Circle of Willis variations and neurological disorders, such as stroke, aneurysm, and cognitive impairment.
- Studies employing imaging techniques (e.g., angiography, MRI, CT) to identify and characterize anatomical variations.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Case reports or case series.
- Reviews, meta-analyses, commentaries, editorials and letters.
- Studies that do not provide quantitative data on anatomical variations.
- Studies involving pediatric population.
- Studies done on animals.

A pre-screening or pilot literature review was meticulously conducted to ensure the reliability and credibility of the literature selection process. This pre-screening was performed by two independent researchers, and discrepancies were settled by a third researcher. Title and abstract of each study were thoroughly examined to ascertain its relevance to the research objectives.

Data extraction and synthesis was performed after appropriate screening of the studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The extracted data included publication year, country, sample size, design of the study, mean age of the participants, main findings of the study and conclusion. The collected data were presented as findings of this systematic review after analysis.

Result

Initial search identified 1339 studies from the databases and other sources. 1061 records were screened after initial exclusion of the studies. Following an assessment of the titles and abstracts, 57 articles were selected for further consideration. Following that, 37 studies were eliminated based on the inclusion criteria and three studies were not in English. We screened 20 studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Finally, we selected 14 studies because of non-availability of some data in the other studies. The process of selection of the studies is depicted in the PRISMA study selection diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Chart

Table 1: Included studies on anatomical variations in the circle of Willis

Authors & Publication Year	Country	Sample Size/ Design of the Study	Mean Age (Years)	Findings	Conclusion
Naveen SR et al.; 2015 [8]	India	300 patients; Prospective and retrospective study	55 years	Complete circle of Willis (CW) was seen in 16.6% patients. Incomplete anterior and posterior CW was found in 22%, 61.3% had partially complete CW configuration. Most common anterior variant is type A (normal anterior configuration) with a prevalence of 66%. The most common posterior circle variant is type E (hypoplasia or absence of both PcomA) with 32.6%.	The prevalence of complete configuration of the circle of Willis (CW) is 16.6%; slightly higher in females and younger subjects. Complete anterior circle was present in 77.3%. Overall, CW variants are slightly more common among the women in comparison to men.
Jalali Kondori B et al.; 2017 [9]	Iran	525 healthy participants; Cross-sectional study	51.5 years	Complete circle of Willis was visible in a small number of patients. The circle of Willis had a complete vascular structure in	This study reported wide variations in the circle of Willis. Most variations are related to the posterior part of the cir-

				20.9% of the patients. The anterior part of the circle of Willis had a complete structure in 80.95% of the cases, while the posterior part had a complete structure in 20.95% of the cases.	cle of Willis. Absence of bilateral posterior communicating artery variation is more common than other types of variations in this population.
Shaikh R et al.; 2018 [10]	Pakistan	135 subjects; Descriptive cross-sectional study	49.26 years	22.2% showed a complete circle, while 60.7% and 17.1% had partially complete and incomplete circles respectively. The anterior part of the circle was completed in 80% subjects, showing type 'a' as the most common variant in 68.9%. The posterior part of the circle was completed in 22.2% subjects with type 'e' variant in 38.5%.	There was a wide variability in the anatomy of the Circle of Willis in Pakistani adults asymptomatic for cerebrovascular disease.
Ravikanth R et al.; 2019 [11]	India	200 patients; Descriptive study	48.5 years	Anterior variant type A and posterior variant type E were most common types of Circle of Willis. Type A in the anterior circulation is the normal adult pattern. There is a single anterior communicating artery. Type E in the posterior circulation is hypoplasia or absence of both posterior communicating arteries and isolation of the anterior and posterior parts of the circle at this level.	Configuration of the CW may vary greatly in the general population. Overall, CW variants were slightly more common in women than in men.
Zaki SM et al.; 2019 [12]	Egypt	100 patients	Not Available	Complete, partially complete and incomplete COW were observed in 28%, 38% and 34% respectively. 56% was the classical type "a", 24% was type "g" (hypoplasia or aplasia of the anterior communicating artery).	The prevalence of complete COW was 28%. Variations of COW were found to be more common in the posterior circulation (62%). The incomplete anterior circle was found in 34% and it is mostly caused by hypoplasia or aplasia of the anterior communicating artery.
Machasio RM et al.; 2019 [13]	Kenya.	94 patients; Cross-sectional descriptive study	Not Available	37.2% of patients had a Complete Circle of Willis, with Type A variant being the most	The findings in this study demonstrate slight differences in the Circle of Willis

				common anterior variant. Fetal PCA was present in 25.5%, and aneurysms were present in 24.5% of patients. ACoA aneurysms were common at 43.6%. AVMs were present in 8.5% of patients. No significant association was found between aneurysms/AVMs and CW configuration.	configuration. A higher proportion of complete anterior Circle of Willis was seen in female patients.
Dhakal P et al.; 2020 [14]	Nepal	95 patients; A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study	50 years	Anatomical variations in the arteries of Circle of Willis was seen 54.7% patients, hypoplastic posterior communicating artery being the most common variation 34.7%. Aneurysm was seen in 23.2% of cases	CT Angiography is a common imaging method for suspected cerebral aneurysms and other vascular pathologies, as it can detect variations in Circle of Willis arteries, crucial for operative management.
Hindenes LB et al.; 2020 [15]	Norway	1,864 subjects; Cohort study	65.4 years	Only about 12% of the adult population have a complete Circle of Willis, while the remaining 88% have one or more missing segments, thus reducing their collateral capacity.	This study demonstrated age is associated with Circle of Willis variants, suggesting reduced collateral capacity with older age.
Wijesinghe P et al.; 2020 [16]	Sri Lanka	73 patients; Cadaveric study	67.7 years	93% of elderly brains had at least one hypoplastic CW component at death, with most variations in communicating arteries and proximal posterior and anterior cerebral arteries. Arterial bifurcations were the primary sites for cerebral aneurysms, and over 90% of the brains had CW atherosclerosis.	CW abnormalities were predominant in the ageing Sri Lankan brains.
De Caro J et al.; 2021 [17]	Italy	1131 patients; Retrospective study	72 years	62.1% showed vascular variants among stroke patients, compared 54.8% of the control group. 23.5% of patients had an anterior circulation variant, 54.7% had a posterior circulation variant, and 21.8% had both. The most prevalent variant was agenesis/ hypoplasia of the anterior cerebral arteries	The prevalence of variants of circle of Willis was higher in ischemic stroke patients compared to controls.

				(17.8%), followed by unilateral fetal type of the posterior cerebral arteries (12.11%).	
Dumitrescu AM et al.; 2022 [18]	Romania	96 fresh available circles of Willis obtained at clinical autopsy; descriptive observational study	Not clear	70.82% cases presented the typical CoW and only 29.18% were “atypical” or “with anatomical variants”. The most frequent anatomical variants were hypoplasia (20.91%), followed by the absence of an artery (3.06%), and partially fetal type artery (2.04%). 67.86% of atypical CoW exhibited more than one anatomical variant of an artery in one circle.	Anatomical variations of circles of Willis are very polymorphic in the Northeastern part of Romania. Hypoplasia of an artery was the most common anatomical variant in these circles of Willis.
Diljohn J et al.; 2023 [4]	Trinidad	152 participants; prospective, descriptive, cross-sectional study	46.4 years	A complete circle of Willis (CoW) was seen in 24.3%. The most common variations in the anterior and posterior parts of the circle were a hypoplastic anterior communicating artery (8.6%) and bilateral aplastic posterior communicating arteries (18.4%), respectively.	Significant variations exist in the CoW of a south Trinidad population with a frequency of complete in 24.3%, and more complete circles in younger patients and Afro-Trinidadians. Gender did not influence CoW morphology.
Enyedi M et al.; 2023 [19]	Romania	126 individuals; retrospective cohort study	36 years	In 30.9% of cases, a classical configuration of the Circle of Willis (CoW) was found, with the most common variation being the unilateral absence of a posterior communicating artery. A complete entire CoW was found in 63 cases, and complete configurations were found in 108 and 73 cases, respectively. Eight cases did not present complete configurations, and a foetal posterior communicating artery was identified unilaterally in 14 cases and bilaterally in six cases.	Unilateral variations were the most common changes found in CoW configuration.
Sibiya, G et al.; 2024 [20]	South Africa	239 patients; Retrospective study	65.7 years	Complete CoW was found in 74.23% of cases, with variations in 10.84%. Cerebral arter-	Morphologic variations in the configuration of the cerebral arteries and the

				ies and CoW normal morphology were classified as complete, absent, or hypoplastic. ACA A1 was absent in 4.91%, hypoplastic in 30.40%, and fenestrated in 1.06%.	CoW are common in the South African population. ACA is the most variable of all the arteries; hypoplasia was the most prevalent variation.
--	--	--	--	---	--

Table 1 outlines various studies on the Circle of Willis (CoW) across different countries, with findings related to its anatomical variations, prevalence, and demographics. The table presents a collection of studies conducted across various countries, focusing on the anatomical variations of the Circle of Willis (CoW), sample sizes, mean ages, findings, and conclusions.

Each study lists the authors and year of publication, establishing a wide range of research conducted over the years, from 2015 to 2024. The studies span multiple countries, including India, Iran, Pakistan, Egypt, Kenya, Nepal, Norway, Sri Lanka, Italy, Romania, Trinidad, and South Africa, reflecting a diverse geographic representation.

Sample sizes vary significantly, from as low as 73 to as high as 1,864 participants. The designs include cross-sectional studies, prospective studies, retrospective studies, descriptive studies, and cohort studies. The average age of participants in different studies ranges from approximately 36 to 72 years, indicating varying demographics across studies. The prevalence of a complete Circle of Willis ranges broadly, with values from as low as 12% in Norway to as high as 74.23% in South Africa. The anterior and posterior configurations report varying common types, with Type A frequently identified as the most common anterior variant, while hypoplasia of posterior communicating arteries is a common variant in multiple regions. Other variations include the presence of aneurysms, which are noted in some studies.

Discussion

The findings of the current systematic review regarding the anatomical variations of the Circle of Willis (CoW) across different studies reveal significant insights into its prevalence, configuration, and variations. The prevalence of a complete Circle of Willis varies significantly among populations. For instance, Naveen SR et al. [8] reported only 16.6% of patients in India had a complete CoW, while Sibiyi G et al. [20] found a remarkably higher prevalence of 74.23% in South Africa. This discrepancy suggests that geographic and ethnic factors may influence the anatomical characteristics of the CoW.

The most common anterior variant across several studies is Type A (normal configuration), with

varying prevalence. For example, it was reported at 66% in Naveen SR et al. [8] and 78.7% in Machasio RM et al. [13]. The posterior variant Type E (hypoplasia or absence of both posterior communicating arteries) was frequently noted, with Naveen SR et al. identifying it in 32.6% of cases. Studies consistently report high rates of incomplete configurations. For instance, Zaki SM et al. [12] found that 34% of patients had an incomplete anterior circle, which aligns with findings from other studies indicating significant variability in the posterior part of the CoW.

Age appears to be a significant factor influencing the prevalence of CoW variants. Hindenes LB et al. [15] noted that only 12% of the adult population had a complete CoW, with older age associated with increased variants. Furthermore, some studies, like Naveen SR et al. [8], suggest that variants are more common in women, although this is not universally observed.

Variations in the CoW are prevalent, with studies reporting a range of anomalies such as hypoplasia and aplasia of various arteries. For example, Dhakal P et al. [14] highlighted that 54.7% of patients had anatomical variations, with hypoplastic posterior communicating arteries being the most common. The study conducted by Jalali Kondori B et al. [9] supports the finding of high variability, reporting that only 20.9% of participants had a complete CoW, with most variations occurring in the posterior part. This aligns with Naveen SR et al. [8], reinforcing the idea that the posterior CoW is particularly prone to variations. The study of Machasio RM et al. [13] corroborates the prevalence of Type A as the dominant anterior variant and emphasizes the presence of Type E as a significant posterior variant. It also highlights the occurrence of fetal PCA, indicating a complex landscape of anatomical configurations. De Caro J et al. [17] found a higher prevalence of vascular variants among stroke patients compared to controls, supporting the notion that anatomical variations can significantly impact cerebrovascular health.

Hindenes LB et al. [15] concluded that only 12% of the population has a complete CoW contradicts the higher prevalence reported in Sibiyi G et al. [20]. This suggests that population-specific factors, such as genetics and environmental influences, may play a crucial role in the anatomical characteristics of

the CoW. Zaki SM et al. [12] reported 28% prevalence of complete CoW contrasts with the lower figures from Naveen SR et al. [8] and Hindenes LB et al. [15]. This discrepancy raises questions about the consistency of findings across different populations and methodologies. Diljohn J et al. [4] investigated that 24.3% of participants had a complete CoW is lower than the 74.23% reported by Sibiya G et al. [20] and suggests that regional differences may significantly affect the prevalence of complete configurations.

Clinical Implications

Understanding the anatomical variations of the CoW is crucial for several reasons. Variations can significantly impact neurosurgical approaches, necessitating preoperative imaging to identify potential complications [5, 4]. Studies have shown that individuals with variations, particularly in the PCoA and AComA, are at a higher risk for ischemic strokes. Specifically, the presence of PCoA hypoplasia has been correlated with increased incidences of thalamic infarcts [3,21]. Variations in the CoW are frequently observed in patients with aneurysms, particularly at the AComA and PComA. The presence of hypoplastic segments has been linked to both the formation and rupture of these aneurysms [21].

Conclusion

This systematic review indicates a complex landscape of anatomical variations in the Circle of Willis, with significant differences in the prevalence of complete and incomplete configurations across various populations. The anatomical variations of the Circle of Willis are complex and influenced by various demographic factors, including geography, age, and gender.

While many studies support the notion of high variability and the predominance of certain configurations, contradictions in prevalence rates highlight the need for further research. Understanding these variations is crucial for clinicians in diagnosing and managing cerebrovascular conditions, as well as in planning surgical interventions. Further investigation is warranted to reconcile these differences and enhance our understanding of the anatomical variations of the Circle of Willis.

References

1. Jones JD, Castanho P, Bazira P, Sanders K. Anatomical variations of the circle of Willis and their prevalence, with a focus on the posterior communicating artery: A literature review and meta-analysis. *Clin Anat*. 2021 Oct; 34(7):978-990. doi: 10.1002/ca.23662.
2. Iqbal S. A comprehensive study of the anatomical variations of the circle of willis in adult human brains. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2013 Nov; 7(11):2423-7. doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2013/6580.3563.
3. Haghghimorad, M., Bahrami-Motlagh, H., Salehi, E. et al. Anatomical variations in posterior part of the circle of Willis and their associations with brain infarct in different vascular territories. *Egypt J Radiol Nucl Med* 53, 51 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43055-022-00728-w>
4. Diljohn J, Rampersad F, Maharaj P, Parmesar K. Anatomical variations in the circle of Willis on magnetic resonance angiography in a south Trinidad population. *BJR Open*. 2023 Dec 12; 6(1):tzad002. doi: 10.1093/bjro/tzad002.
5. Singh, R., Kannabathula, A. B., Sunam, H. & Deka, D. Anatomical variations of circle of Willis- a cadaveric study. *Int. Surg. J.* 4(4), 1249–1258 (2017).
6. Hindenes LB, Ingebrigtsen T, Isaksen JG, Håberg AK, Johnsen LH, Herder M, Mathiesen EB, Vangberg TR. Anatomical variations in the circle of Willis are associated with increased odds of intracranial aneurysms: The Tromsø study. *J Neurol Sci*. 2023 Sep 15; 452:120740. doi: 10.1016/j.jns.2023.120740.
7. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021 Mar 29; 372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.
8. Naveen SR, Bhat V, Karthik GA. Magnetic resonance angiographic evaluation of circle of Willis: A morphologic study in a tertiary hospital set up. *Ann Indian Acad Neurol*. 2015 Oct-Dec; 18(4):391-7. doi: 10.4103/0972-2327.165453.
9. Jalali Kondori B, Azemati F, Dadseresht S. Magnetic Resonance Angiographic Study of Anatomic Variations of the Circle of Willis in a Population in Tehran. *Arch Iran Med*. 2017 Apr; 20(4):235-239.
10. Shaikh R, Sohail S. MRA-based evaluation of anatomical variation of circle of Willis in adult Pakistanis. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2018 Feb; 68(2):187-191.
11. Ravikanth R, Philip B. Magnetic resonance angiography determined variations in the circle of Willis: Analysis of a large series from a single center. *Ci Ji Yi Xue Za Zhi*. 2019 Jan-Mar; 31(1):52-59. doi: 10.4103/tcmj.tcmj_167_17.
12. Zaki SM, Shaaban MH, Abd Al Galeel WA, El Hussein AAW. Configuration of the circle of Willis and its two parts among Egyptian: a magnetic resonance angiographic study. *Folia Morphol (Warsz)*. 2019; 78(4):703-709. doi: 10.5603/FM.a2019.0015. Epub 2019 Feb 14. PMID: 30761512.
13. Machasio RM, Nyabanda R, Mutala TM. Proportion of Variant Anatomy of the Circle of Willis and Association with Vascular Anoma-

- lies on Cerebral CT Angiography. *Radiol Res Pract.* 2019 Jun 16; 2019:6380801. doi: 10.1155/2019/6380801.
14. Dhakal P, Kayastha P, Paudel S, Suwal S, Sharma MR, Ghimire RK. Anatomical Variations in Circle of Willis in Patients Undergoing CT Cerebral Angiography in a Tertiary Hospital in Nepal: A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *JNMA J Nepal Med Assoc.* 2020 Dec 31; 58(232):1065-1068. doi: 10.31729/jnma.5893.
 15. Hindenes LB, Håberg AK, Johnsen LH, Mathiesen EB, Robben D, Vangberg TR. Variations in the Circle of Willis in a large population sample using 3D TOF angiography: The Tromsø Study. *PLoS One.* 2020 Nov 3; 15(11):e0241373. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0241373.
 16. Wijesinghe P, Steinbusch HWM, Shankar SK, Yasha TC, De Silva KRD. Circle of Willis abnormalities and their clinical importance in ageing brains: A cadaveric anatomical and pathological study. *J Chem Neuroanat.* 2020 Jul; 106:101772. doi: 10.1016/j.jchemneu.2020.101772.
 17. De Caro J, Ciacciarelli A, Tessitore A, Buonomo O, Calzoni A, Francalanza I, Dell'Aera C, Cosenza D, Currò CT, Granata F, Vinci SL, Trimarchi G, Toscano A, Musolino RF, La Spina P. Variants of the circle of Willis in ischemic stroke patients. *J Neurol.* 2021 Oct; 268(10):3799-3807. doi: 10.1007/s00415-021-10454-4.
 18. Dumitrescu AM, Eva L, Haba D, Cucu AI, Dumitrescu GF, Burduloi VM, Dima-Cozma LC, Vatavu R, Moroşanu GC, Sava A. Anatomical study of circle of Willis on fresh autopsied brains. A study of a Romanian population. *Rom J Morphol Embryol.* 2022 Apr-Jun; 63(2):395-406. doi: 10.47162/RJME.63.2.10.
 19. Enyedi M, Scheau C, Baz RO, Didilescu AC. Circle of Willis: anatomical variations of configuration. A magnetic resonance angiography study. *Folia Morphol (Warsz).* 2023; 82(1):24-29. doi: 10.5603/FM.a2021.0134.
 20. Sibiyá, G., Omotoso, B.R., Harrichandparsad, R. et al. exploring the anatomical configurations of the cerebral arteries in a cohort of South African patients. *Sci Rep* 14, 6060 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-56767-y>
 21. Feng L, Mao HJ, Zhang DD, Zhu YC, Han F. Anatomical variations in the Circle of Willis and the formation and rupture of intracranial aneurysms: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Neurol.* 2023 Jan 16; 13:1098950. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2022.1098950.